

Underactuated Cable-Driven Parallel Robots: Exploiting and Controlling the Free Motion

Edoardo Idà, Marco Carricato

Dept. of Industrial Engineering, IRMA L@B, University of Bologna
 {edoardo.ida2,marco.carricato}@unibo.it, <https://irmalab.org/>

Abstract—This paper summarizes some relevant kinematic and dynamic properties of Underactuated Cable-driven Parallel Robots that lead these manipulators to freely oscillate. Details on how oscillations can be controlled while performing a task, or exploited for identification purposes, are reported.

Index Terms—Cable-driven parallel robots, underactuated robots, underconstrained robots, trajectory planning, frequency analysis, input shaping, parameter identification

I. INTRODUCTION

Cable-Driven Parallel Robots (*CDPRs*) are parallel robots which use cables in place of rigid extensible legs in order to move an end-effector (*EE*). *CDPRs* present specific advantages over traditional parallel robots, such as remarkably large workspaces[1]. Since guaranteeing positive tensions in cables is a necessary requisite to control the pose of the robot, the unilateral constraints imposed by cables complicate the system control.

Under the assumption that cables are inextensible and massless, *CDPRs* can be classified, from the perspective of the robot ability to constrain the *EE*, by comparing the number n of independently controlled cables with the degrees of freedom n_d (*DoFs*) of the *EE*:

- if $n = n_d$, when all cables are taut, the manipulator is completely-constrained, since the *EE* configuration is fully determined by cable lengths, and the solution of the inverse dynamic (or static) problem allows a single set of cable tensions to be computed [2], [3], [4];
- if $n > n_d$, when all cables are taut, the robot is redundantly-constrained, and the inverse dynamic (or static) problem admits infinite solutions [5], [6];
- if $n < n_d$, the robot is underconstrained [7], and the *EE* configuration does not depend only on geometric constraints (i.e. actuator displacements), but also on mechanical equilibrium, namely the external loads that the *EE* is acted upon.

The use of *CDPRs* equipped with a limited number of cables, that are usually routed towards the *EE* from an elevated position (thus forming suspended and underactuated *CDPRs*, or *UACDPRs*, Fig. 1), is justified in several applications, in which the task to be performed requires a limited number of controlled freedoms or a limitation of mobility is acceptable in order to enhance accessibility, decrease complexity, and ultimately cost. *UACDPRs* are intrinsically underconstrained [8], since their *EE* is subject to less constraint actions than the number of its *DoFs*. As

Figure 1: Underactuated suspended *CDPR*

a consequence, the *EE* preserves some freedoms once the actuators are locked, a condition that is referred as *free motion*, which results in *EE natural oscillations*. *UACDPRs* received increasing attention in the last decade, when their equilibrium configurations, and equilibrium stability, resulting from the so-called *geometrico-static* model, were analyzed [8], [9], [10], [11], [12]. In the following, a brief summary of University of Bologna work on free-motion modelling, exploitation, and control is reported.

II. MODELLING NATURAL OSCILLATIONS

A *UACDPR* consists of a mobile platform coupled to the base by $n < 6$ cables, which can be coiled and uncoiled by motorized winches. If l_i ($i = 1, \dots, n$) is the length of each cable, and ζ is the *EE* pose, each taut cable imposes a geometrical constraint $\varphi_i(l_i, \zeta) = 0$ on the platform. If \mathbf{l} is the array stacking all cable lengths, \mathbf{v} is the *EE* twist, and Ξ is the manipulator geometric Jacobian, differentiating all geometrical constraints with respect to time yields:

$$\Xi \mathbf{v} - \dot{\mathbf{l}} = \mathbf{0}_{n \times 1} \quad (1)$$

Since the robot is underactuated, Ξ is rectangular, and, out of singularities, $\text{rank}(\Xi) = n < 6$. Thus, only n coordinates of the *EE* pose can be controlled by varying the *UACDPR* cable lengths, while the remaining $\lambda = 6 - n$ are to be determined through the mechanical equilibrium of the *EE*. In addition, even if the actuators are locked and cable lengths are kept constant, λ freedoms remains. The n

controlled coordinates are denoted as ζ_c , whereas the non-controllable coordinates are named *free coordinates* and denoted as ζ_f . For simplicity, we group the elements of ζ so that $\zeta = [\zeta_c^T \zeta_f^T]^T$. It was recently shown [7], [12] that, by suitably computing the geometric Jacobian nullspace Ξ^\perp , and right inverse Ξ^\parallel , the *EE* twist can be expressed as:

$$\mathbf{v} = \mathbf{v}_f + \mathbf{v}_c = \Xi^\perp \dot{\zeta}_f + \Xi^\parallel \dot{\mathbf{i}} \quad (2)$$

$$\mathbf{v}_f = \Xi^\perp \dot{\zeta}_f, \quad \mathbf{v}_c = \Xi^\parallel \dot{\mathbf{i}} \quad (3)$$

where \mathbf{v}_f and \mathbf{v}_c are called *free twist* and *controlled twist*, respectively. The latter is the twist due to cable actuation, and, if the robot configuration is known, it can be prescribed; the former is the twist due to the *EE* free motion, and can be analyzed, exploited, or controlled, only by taking into account the *EE* dynamics.

The dynamic model of the *UACDPR* emerges from the *EE* mechanical equilibrium, subject to cable constraints, inertial actions, and a generic external wrench:

$$\mathbf{M}\dot{\mathbf{v}} + \mathbf{C}\mathbf{v} = -\Xi^T \boldsymbol{\tau} + \mathbf{f} \quad (4)$$

where \mathbf{M} is the *EE* mass matrix, \mathbf{C} is the Coriolis matrix, $\boldsymbol{\tau}$ is the array of cable tensions, and \mathbf{f} is an external wrench applied on the *EE*. Pre-multiplying (4) by $\Xi^{\perp T}$, the *EE* internal-dynamics is obtained, which is a second-order non-holonomic constraint on the *EE* configuration variables, independent of the cable tensions [13], [7]:

$$\Xi^{\perp T} (\mathbf{M}\dot{\mathbf{v}} + \mathbf{C}\mathbf{v} - \mathbf{f}) = \mathbf{0}_{\lambda \times 1} \quad (5)$$

These λ equations, along with the n geometrical constraints, allow to analyze *UACDPRs* in the Cartesian space. By substituting (2) (and its derivative) in (5), *UACDPRs* can be analyzed in the joint space:

$$\mathbf{M}^\perp \dot{\zeta}_f + \mathbf{M}_I^\perp \ddot{\mathbf{i}} + \mathbf{C}^\perp \dot{\zeta}_f + \mathbf{C}_I^\perp \dot{\mathbf{i}} + \mathbf{f}^\perp = \mathbf{0}_{\lambda \times 1} \quad (6)$$

$$\mathbf{M}^\perp = \Xi^{\perp T} \mathbf{M} \Xi^\perp, \quad \mathbf{M}_I^\perp = \Xi^{\perp T} \mathbf{M} \Xi^\parallel, \quad \mathbf{f}^\perp = -\Xi^{\perp T} \mathbf{f} \quad (7)$$

$$\mathbf{C}^\perp = \Xi^{\perp T} (\mathbf{M} \dot{\Xi}^\perp + \mathbf{C} \Xi^\perp), \quad \mathbf{C}_I^\perp = \Xi^{\perp T} (\mathbf{M} \dot{\Xi}^\parallel + \mathbf{C} \Xi^\parallel) \quad (8)$$

Equation (6) is particularly useful to analyse free motion ($\dot{\mathbf{i}} = \ddot{\mathbf{i}} = \mathbf{0}_{n \times 1}$), since its linearization about an equilibrium configuration (denoted by the subscript 0):

$$\mathbf{M}_0^\perp \Delta \ddot{\zeta}_{f0} + \mathbf{K}_0^\perp \Delta \zeta_{f0} = \mathbf{0}_{\lambda \times 1} \quad (9)$$

allows to compute the *EE* natural oscillation frequencies by solving the associated eigenproblem [7].

III. EXPLOITING AND CONTROLLING NATURAL OSCILLATIONS

While performing a task, *EE* natural oscillations needs to be limited. We investigated two approaches, based on trajectory planning of the controlled coordinates of the system. The first approach is based on the (approximate) knowledge of the *EE* natural-oscillation frequencies along the path to be followed: in this case, trajectories are planned by using *Input Shaping* techniques [7], and the trajectory

time is optimized by means of *Dynamic Scaling* [14]. This method has the advantage to be real-time compatible, but the drawback of only limiting *EE* oscillations. On the contrary, *rest-to-rest* planners [13], which are based on the solution of a boundary value problem arising from (5), allow oscillation-free trajectories to be computed, but require time-consuming offline planning.

The aforementioned planners require the precise knowledge of the *EE* inertial parameters, thus their identification was explored in [15]. It was shown that, by exciting and recording the *EE* free oscillatory motion, identification can be carried out without force or torque measurements, which simplifies the experimental set-up. Currently, free motion is being investigated for geometric calibration purposes.

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